

ISic0652

I.Sicily inscription 0652

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary; honorific

Material

limestone

Object

block

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

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Autopsy

2013.10.03

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Ortygia

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 50115

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI332861

1. [ὄμματαδ'ο]ἰ παῖδες θλίβουσι πεσὴ [ματιτοῦδεῖνος]
2. [ὄσλύπαις] καὶ νούσοις ἥπια φάρμακα πᾶσιν
3. [ᾠπασενε]ὑδαίμων· τοῦ μὲν κλέος οὔποτ' ὀλίται
4. [ῆως καὶ τ]ε δύσις μεγάλων μεμνήσεται ἔργων

Apparatus

Text via PHI

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644892

PHI 331828

Bibliography

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Archival photograph